

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF FIBRE-METAL LAMINATES SUBJECT TO IMPACT DAMAGE

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1 Introduction

Fibre-Metal Laminates (FMLs) are a hybrid of metal and composite laminates that are increasingly being used in aerospace applications. Consisting of alternating layers of thin metallic sheets and fibre-reinforced epoxy composite prepreg, the two main types of FML are aramid fibre-reinforced epoxy/aluminium laminates (ARALL) and S-2 glass fibre-reinforced epoxy/aluminium laminates (GLARE). The combination of mechanical properties of monolithic metal and fibre-reinforced composite provides FMLs with mechanical advantages such as low density, high strength, and high damage tolerance.

Impact damage is a key concern for aerospace structures. The inability to visually detect interior damage to composite layers, sometimes extending well beyond the impacted area, remains an important safety issue. Therefore it is necessary to accurately predict internal impact damage to FMLs. Due to out-of-plane loads, such as impacts, FMLs may suffer damage in the form of different mechanisms such as: (i) plastic deformation of the metal layers; (ii) matrix cracking and fibre failure; (iii) delamination between composite plies; and (iv) debonding of the metal and composite layer.

A Finite Element (FE) model was developed to analyse the complex damage responses and deformation that lead to the strength and stiffness loss of FML structures. The accuracy achieved through FE analysis increases the reliability of numerical models to simulate impact loads onto FMLs, enabling the reduction of time and costs associated with mechanical testing.

2 Numerical Modelling

2.1 Modelling Strategy

Numerical analysis was conducted using the commercial finite element solver Abaqus/Explicit [1] for the evaluation of impact damage to the FML specimens. Hexahedral solid elements (C3D8R) were used for the aluminium layers. The isotropic elastic-plastic properties of aluminium were modeled using the isotropic plasticity model in Abaqus.

Hexahedral continuum shell elements (SC8R), each having eight nodes and three degrees of freedom, were used for the glass/epoxy composite ply layers. In order to accurately analyse the through-thickness shear stresses resulting from the impact, continuum shell elements were selected over standard 4-node shell elements [2]. Due to the excessive distortions of elements, an enhanced stiffness relaxation method was applied for hourglass control [1]. The Hashin [3] failure criterion was implemented in Abaqus to model the progressive intralaminar damage of the composite layers due to impact.

The adhesive bond between the glass/epoxy plies and aluminium sheets was modelled using the traction-separation cohesive law in Abaqus to represent the mechanical response of the adhesive under impact loading. The thickness of the adhesive is considered negligible in this analysis, and therefore the surface-based cohesive contact capability was used to model the delamination. A detailed element sensitivity study for the numerical models was conducted using the different element selections available in Abaqus.

2.2 Model Validation

Wu [4] conducted a series of low velocity impact tests to evaluate the deformation and damage responses of FMLs. A comparative study was conducted using the experimental impact results of Wu [4] for Glare 5 2/1 to validate the numerical model predictions. Glare 5 2/1 consists of two layers of Al 2024-T3 aluminium alloy sheet and one layer of [0/90/90/0] glass/epoxy composite. Fig. 1 shows the Glare 5 2/1 lay-up configuration used by Wu [4]. A $76 \times 76 \text{ mm}^2$ square test FML specimen was clamped between two steel plates exposing a circular central impact region with a diameter of 50 mm. A steel spherical impactor of 16 mm diameter with a mass of 6.29 kg was used with impact energies varying from 7 to 40 J.

Fig.1. Glare 5 2/1 lay-up configuration [5]

Comparison for contact force-time histories for Glare 5 2/1 subject to impact showed good agreement between the experimental results [4] and numerical predictions, as shown in Fig.2. The force-time history for Glare 5 2/1 shows the characteristic initial rise in force to a maximum value, followed by a sudden load drop. The sudden load drops after peak force indicates the local strength of the FML structure was reached and energy starts to dissipate in the form of irreversible damage to the aluminium and glass/epoxy layers [6]. At 24.2 J, the experimental results show a sharp load drop at 3 ms. Despite the incorporation of the Hashin failure criteria in Abaqus, the numerically predicted force-time history did not replicate the sharp load drop, characteristic of the stiffness degradation at this impact energy. This may be due to the cracking of the non-impacted aluminium side of the FML structure which is not explicitly modelled in the FE model [5].

Fig.2. Comparison of numerically predicted force-time history of Glare 5 2/1 and experimental results [4] for varying impact energies

Further comparison was conducted on the impact damage region of glass-epoxy composite and plastic deformation of the non-impacted side of the aluminium. Fig. 3. shows the increase in damage area for Glare 5 2/1 with an increase in impact energy. The numerical model shows good agreement with the experimental results of Wu [4]. From this comparison, the FE model satisfied the validation process showing the capability to accurately analyse the impact event and subsequent damage area of FML structures.

Fig.3. Comparison of experimental results [4] and numerically predicted damage area as a function of impact energy

3. Numerical Analysis

A FE model was developed to analyse the impact event and resulting damage of FMLs. Studies were conducted on two FML variants: FML 3 [Al/0/90/Al/0/90/Al] and FML 5 [Al/0/90/90/0/Al]. Specimens were modelled using Al 2024-T3 aluminium alloy and S2 glass/epoxy prepreg. The average thickness of each aluminium layer was 0.406 mm and each ply of S2 glass/epoxy prepreg was 0.3 mm thick. Two sides of the specimen were clamped. Taking advantage of the symmetry, only one-quarter of the FML test specimen was modelled with appropriate boundary conditions applied. The mass and diameter of the spherical steel impactor were 6.15 kg and 12.7 mm, respectively. The impact energies ranged from 10 to 30 J.

Isotropic elastic properties for the Aluminium 2024-T3 are: Young's Modulus $E = 73800$ MPa and Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.33$. The unidirectional glass/epoxy composite exhibits transversely isotropic behavior [7]. The corresponding elastic properties, ultimate stresses and fracture energies for the glass/epoxy are given in Table 1-3. The material properties of the adhesive used in the FE analysis are shown in Table 4. The traction-separation cohesive law is characterised in terms of peak failure strengths, t_n^f and t_s^f and fracture energies G_n and G_s , where n and s refer to the normal (Mode 1) and shear (Mode 2) directions [7].

Table 1
Elastic material properties of glass/epoxy [7-10]

Materials	Parameter Values, GPa					
	E_{11}	E_{22}	G_{12}	G_{23}	ν_{12}	ν_{23}
S2 glass/epoxy	55	9.5	5.5	3	0.33	0.33

Table 2
Ultimate strength properties for unidirectional glass/epoxy [7-10]

Parameter value, MPa					
$\sigma_L^{u,t}$	$\sigma_L^{u,c}$	$\sigma_T^{u,t}$	$\sigma_T^{u,c}$	$\tau_{LT}^u = \tau_{TT}^u$	
2430	2000	50	160	50	

Table 3
Fracture energies for glass/epoxy [7]

Parameter value, N/mm			
$G_{fl,t}$	$G_{fl,c}$	$G_{ft,t}$	$G_{ft,c}$
12.5	12.5	1.0	1.0

Table 4
Material properties of adhesive [7]

E	ν	t_n^f	t_s^f	G_n	G_s
MPa		MPa	MPa	N/mm	N/mm
2000	0.33	50	50	4.0	4.0

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Impactor force versus time history

The impactor force-time history calculated using the FE model is shown in Fig.4 for FML 3 and FML 5. After impact initiation, the impactors velocity is reduced as it comes in contact with the FML structure. This deceleration of the impactor is associated with the reaction-force on the impactor as kinetic energy is transferred to the FML structure. Small changes in the slope of the force-time histories for FML 3 and FML 5 are suspected to be caused by the start of delamination and fibre failure [11].

The small load drops seen at 3.9 ms in Fig. 4b. correspond to fibre fracture in the glass/epoxy plies shown in Fig. 5. Although no sharp load drops indicating cracking of the outer non-impacted aluminium were seen to occur for both variations of FML, analysis of the plastic strain in Fig. 6. shows significant damage of the outer aluminium layer in the impact region. No full impactor penetration was recorded at these impact energies.

Fig.4. Impactor force-time histories of a) FML 3 and b) FML 5

Fig.5. Numerically predicted fibre tensile failure contours of FML 3 at 30 J after a) 1.7, b) 3.9, c) 6.0 and d) 10 ms after initiation of impact

Fig. 6. Numerically predicted plastic strain contours on non-impacted aluminium side of FML 3 at 30 J

4.2 Damage Progression

Damage analysis of the FML panels after impact allowed for intralaminar failure of the S2 glass-epoxy composite prepreg to be identified. The main

failure modes for the prepreg were fibre failure and delamination. Fig. 5. shows a cross-section of the fibre tensile failure contours of the glass-epoxy plies of FML 3 after initiation of impact. The damage variables applied to the numerical model assume values between zero (undamaged) and one (fully damaged). The red contours in Fig. 5. and 7 show complete fibre tensile failure of glass/epoxy plies. Fig. 5a shows fibre breakage initiated at a position directly under the impactor at 1.7 ms after initiation of impact. In Fig. 5c, which corresponds to the maximum impactor penetration, extensive fibre damage is seen to occur, over a large area under the impact region. Delamination is also seen to occur. Fig. 6d shows the deformed shape of the glass/epoxy plies after impactor rebound.

Fig.7. Numerically predicted fibre tensile failure contours of last glass-epoxy ply for FML 3 and FML 5 for varying impact energies

The shape of the fibre damage zones in Fig. 7. was predicted to vary depending on the configuration of the FML composite layers. At the lowest impact energy of FML 3, minimum damage to the glass/epoxy composite ply is seen to occur. However, with increasing impact energy, fibre damage grows steadily for both FML variants.

Fig. 8. Numerically predicted central displacement of FML 3 and FML 5

Fig. 8. shows the central displacement as a function of time. The model predicts an increase in impact energy will result in a slightly larger dent depth for both FML 3 and FML 5. FML 5 is also seen to have a larger central displacement compared to FML 3. This may be due to the additional aluminium layer of the FML 3 configuration that provides increased stiffness of the structure.

5 Conclusions

Although there have been many experimental studies conducted on the impact resistance and damage tolerance of FML structures subject to impact, there is limited published work on the development of an accurate numerical model to validate these experimental results in order to predict the structural performance and damage mechanisms of FMLs under impact. The work reported in this paper numerically investigates the performance of glass fibre-reinforced/aluminium laminates under low velocity impact loading for different FML variants.

Impact energies between 10 to 30 J were investigated and resulted in significant damage to both the aluminium and fibre-reinforced epoxy prepreg. The damage consisted of plastic

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deformation of the aluminium layers and fibre breakage, matrix cracking and delamination in the composite. Comparisons of the intralaminar damage associated with impact showed FML 5 configuration had more damage in the form of matrix cracking and fibre tensile failure compared to FML 3. Although the impact energy required to create a visible crack on the non-impacted side of the aluminium layer is higher than what has been studied in this paper, significant plastic deformation on the non-impacted side of the aluminium layer was seen to occur.

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